

Public Sector Use of Private Sector Personal Data: Towards Best Practices

By Teresa Scassa, Canada Research Chair in Information Law and Policy, University of Ottawa

Even as governments explore different options for providing private sector access to (deidentified) public sector personal data, they also seek to benefit from access to stores of personal data held by the private sector. Private sector companies collect a wide array of personal data, often of high volume, rich in detail, and continuously over time. Location and mobility data, for example, are collected by many different companies, from cellular service providers to app developers for diverse purposes. Financial sector organizations amass rich data about the spending and borrowing habits of consumers. The range of available data is constantly broadening as more and more data are collected, and as companies seek secondary markets for the data they collect. Government actors can use these data for a broad range of purposes, ranging from statistics to municipal planning. This paper explores the particular issues raised by public sector access to and use of personal data held by the private sector. It adopts a legal perspective which considers how such data sharing is legally enabled and within what parameters. Given that legal frameworks for data sharing may not always keep pace with data needs and methods, this paper also takes a normative approach which examines whether and in what circumstances such data sharing should take place.

The analysis is framed around two recent examples from the Canadian context that involved attempts by government agencies to access and use personal data held by the private sector for public purposes. Using these two cases as illustrations, the paper will examine the justifications for the use of private sector personal data by government, the safeguards available to protect privacy, and the framing of concerns over the use of these data by different stakeholders. It will identify key issues and propose solutions. Although the examples considered are Canadian and are shaped by the Canadian legal and political context, many of the issues they raise are of broader interest and applicability.

In 2018, Canada's national statistics organization, Statistics Canada (StatCan), acquired detailed credit data from a credit reporting agency relating to over 24 million Canadians. It separately sought access to the banking and credit card records of 500,000 Canadian households. Both projects were designed to generate more accurate and lower cost economic statistical data (Office of the Privacy Commissioner, 2019). Although the credit reporting agency provided the requested data to StatCan, the sector financial institutions resisted, raising over concerns about their own potential liability under the national data protection law. The conflict led to a leak of the project to the media, generating a public outcry and complaints to the federal Privacy Commissioner (Prévost, 2020). These complaints led to an investigation with findings critical of StatCan. The controversy led to changes in how StatCan proposed to approach the gathering of private sector administrative data and the development, in conjunction with the Office of the Privacy

Commissioner of Canada, of a normative framework (Statistics Canada 2020, Office of the Privacy Commissioner, 2019).

In 2022, a further controversy erupted in the media when the public learned that the Public Health Agency of Canada (PHAC) had acquired mobility data analytics about Canadians from two different sources, including one of the country's cellular service providers. PHAC used these analytics to attempt to understand the effectiveness of COVID-19 related restrictions such as lockdowns. The public outcry led to complaints to the Privacy Commissioner of Canada, as well as to hearings before the Parliamentary Standing Committee on Access to Information, Privacy and Ethics (ETHI). These hearings led to a series of recommendations for reform of both laws and practices (Standing Committee, 2022)

Although the nature of the collection or use of data in each of these examples was different, each shares common elements. In each, the institutions seeking to use the data were confident that they had addressed all privacy considerations. In the case of StatCan, this was due to their long-established practices around data confidentiality and privacy. In the case of PHAC, the data acquired were already deidentified according to a reputable process. In both cases, the government agencies believed that the current state of the law permitted their proposed use of the data, even though the laws had been drafted long before this kind of data sharing was contemplated. In both cases, as well, the government agencies did not believe that it was necessary specifically to inform the public of the proposed collection and use of the data.

Each case also highlights some of the issues for private sector data sources. In the case of the financial administrative data, the financial institutions raised concerns about their own potential liability and the impact this type of sharing might have on their relationships with their customers. In the mobility data cases, compliance with data protection law by the private sector analytics suppliers was insufficient to dispel public concerns over the projects. The cases therefore reflect the complexity of issues raised by these types of activities, as well as the insufficiency of data protection alone as a normative framework.

Some have described the issues raised in these examples as ones of "social licence" or trust, rather than individual consent or privacy. As part of its analysis of trust in the use of deidentified data, this paper adopts the theoretical perspective of group privacy (Taylor *et al* 2017). Through this lens, the privacy focus shifts from the individual to the group, and the concept of the identifiable individual is no longer central. Instead, issues of trust require a form of group knowledge and consent to collect and use human-derived data even if it is deidentified. Although group privacy should not be a barrier to public sector uses of private sector data in the public interest, the concept suggests normative content that goes beyond simple 'trust' in government. This paper therefore seeks to understand and identify the elements of that normative content.

The sources of data for this paper include relevant laws and regulations, official reports and studies, information published by the agencies in question, media reports and commentary, and published expert opinions, including parliamentary testimony and expert commentary. Key findings will address: 1) the impact of legislative gaps regarding the sharing of private sector personal data with

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government; 2) the proposed solutions to each of these controversies and an assessment of their merits; 3) how concepts of group privacy bear on these types of data uses; and 4) the elements of an emerging normative framework for the use of private sector data by public sector actors.

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